

Substoichiometric Determination of Cadmium in Water Samples employing Potassium Benzyl Xanthate as a Reagent

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Alkali metal xanthates are used as reagents for the group separation in qualitative analysis¹. Potassium benzyl xanthate is used as an analytical reagent². Literature on extraction of metals using potassium benzyl xanthates is rather limited. Hence, a substoichiometric radiochemical method has been developed for the determination of cadmium. The method has been successfully evaluated for cadmium in different water samples.

Results and Discussion

The extraction behaviour of cadmium : benzyl xanthate was studied under substoichiometric conditions in the pH range 3–7 in acetate buffers. The maximum and quantitative extraction of cadmium-benzyl xanthate complex was found to be at pH 6 in acetate buffers.

The radiometric titration curves are reproducible showing that the substoichiometric isolation is quite satisfactory. The equivalence point indicates the formation of a 1 : 2 complex which can be presented as Cd(BX)₂. Beyond the equivalence point the substoichiometric amount of reagent could always isolate the same amount of cadmium activity from solutions of varying amounts of tracer cadmium. The calibration plot is perfectly linear in the range of 2–16 µg of cadmium and passes through unity on the *a_s/a* axis. The extrapolated portion of the straight-line yields the cadmium content of the tracer solution.

40 µg of Se^{IV}, Te^{IV}, Bi^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Pd^{II}, Cs^I, Tl^I, cyanide, fluoride, citrate, tartrate, phosphate and EDTA do not interfere during the extraction of 20 µg of cadmium under sub-

stoichiometric condition. The interference due to Cu^{II}, Mn^{II} and Ag^I was eliminated with EDTA. In the present method, 1–15 µg of cadmium can be determined with an average error of ± 1.68%.

The results of the analysis of water samples are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM CONTENT OF SAMPLE SOLUTION

Sample	Amount of Cd (µg dm ⁻³)	
	Present method	Standard method
Well water	7.01 ± 0.13	7.24
Bore-well water	6.65 ± 0.11	6.34

*Average of five determinations.

Experimental

A 1 mg ml⁻¹ cadmium solution was prepared from 3CdSO₄·8H₂O (AnalaR) in double-distilled water and standardised³. Cadmium-115m (*t*_{1/2} = 44d) was supplied by the Board of Radiation and Isotope Technology, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. Cadmium tracer solution was prepared by the addition of 20 µl of tracer of 10 ml of stock solution and was made upto 100 ml, which yielded a solution containing 0.1 mg of Cd/ml. A 1.8 × 10⁻³ M potassium benzyl xanthate reagent was prepared in double-distilled methanol.

Different water samples (1 dm³) collected from the industrial area (near Renigunta, Tirupati) were filtered and pre-concentrated to 15 ml by repeated distillation process after treatment with the addition of a few drops of concentrated nitric acid and sulphuric acid. The pre-concentrated solution was fil-

tered again and made upto 25 ml in a standard flask.

The activity measurements were performed by using a G. M. counter. A Elico Li-10 pH meter was used.

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